
Human Resource Management in Improving The Quality of A Productive Educational Environment From Al-Qur'an Perspective; Analysis of Jalalain's Tafsir

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ABSTRACT: Human resource management is the most critical component in running an educational institution to provide quality education. Human resource management actively involves all aspects of an organization's human affairs in achieving established goals. This research aims to explore the Qur'an verses regarding Human Resource Management in Improving the Quality of a Productive Educational Environment from the Qur'anic Perspective: Analysis of Jalalain's Tafsir. This type of research is qualitative research using a literature review. This research uses a thematic approach, combining several verses from the Koran that discuss human resource management and improving the standards of the learning environment. The primary data sources in this research are the Al-Qur'an and Tafsir Jalalain.

Meanwhile, secondary data is taken from books, journal articles, and websites related to the discussion. The data analysis technique uses content analysis. The research results show that human resource management in improving the quality of a productive educational environment is: (1) Totality in human resource development; (2) Justice in human resource management; (3) Responsibility and trust in developing human resources; (4) Increased potential in supporting human resource management and (5) Participation in improving human resources. The conclusions of this study emphasize the importance of taking on the task of increasing the productivity and quality of the educational environment.

KEYWORD: Human resources, quality improvement, productivity, Al-Qur'an, Tafsir Jalalain

INTRODUCTION

To maximize the management of educational institutions, strategic efforts must be made to increase environmental productivity in human resources. Every academic institution needs to be managed well regarding finances, learning, curriculum, facilities, infrastructure, and, most importantly, human resource management. We must be able to engage in healthy, intelligent, and transparent competition with all policy partners, considering current advances in science and technology. Of course, this requires expertise in human resource management. If all the resources on earth are considered, then human resources are the most valuable. Because all of God's creation on earth was deliberately created for the benefit of humanity, humans were created by Allah SWT as caliphs on earth to manage the world and its resources for the welfare of humans themselves, creatures, and the entire universe. Everything in Islam, including the development of human resource management, must follow protocols. Because all levels of Mecca society had not accepted Islam while the Prophet Sallallahu Alaihi Wasallam was there, discussing HRM at that time would be risky, even deadly. Before the people of Medina City acknowledged the existence of his teachings, Rasulullah sallallahu alaihi wasallam began developing human resources and providing guidance through Islamic educational institutions such as mosques, suffahs, and kuttabs. How effectively existing human resources are used for planning and management will determine how Islamic educational institutions develop (Yusri & Amin, 2023).

Based on previous studies regarding how to improve the quality of human resources, (1). According to Ihsan Dacholfany, in line with the goals, vision, and mission of the institution, it is hoped that there will be effective and efficient procedures and management of teaching and educational staff (staff). Developing and practicing management functions, planning and acquiring human resources through evaluating work performance and remuneration, and providing infrastructure through effective coaching and training all contribute to improving the quality of resources. Collaborative partnerships for the progress and growth of educational institutions (Dacholfany, 2017), (2). According to Adri Eferi, he conducted research on environmental assessment both internally and externally when implementing Total Quality Management in Islamic educational institutions. The results of this research significantly impact improving the quality of Islamic educational institutions because they provide insight into

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evaluating the organizational environment from both internal and external points of view (Eferi, 2015), (3). According to Akmal Mundi, the type of dedication to human resources in achieving quality education in Islamic boarding schools can be improved by implementing the attitude commitment method, which focuses on the beliefs and aspirations of the community about the organization. In this case, educators and other staff members in committed schools will demonstrate strong commitment and acceptance of organizational values as part of their work culture. In addition, the business world's commitment to human resources is shown through a related behavioral approach that seeks to improve teaching standards in Islamic boarding schools. Through educational staff such as teachers who are bound by the school's work culture, proven by concrete actions that implement the work culture and organizational principles (Mundi, 2015)

This article aims to provide a deeper explanation of how to improve an educational environment that is productive from an Al-Qur'an perspective and analysis of Tafsir Jalalain by utilizing existing human resources.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative research using a literature review. This research uses a thematic approach, combining several verses from the Koran that discuss human resource management and improving the standards of the learning environment. The primary data sources in this research are the Al-Qur'an and Tafsir Jalalain. Meanwhile, secondary data is taken from books, journal articles, and websites related to the discussion. The data analysis technique uses content analysis. This research aims to find out how human resource management should improve a productive educational environment from the perspective of the Al-Qur'an in the study of Tafsir Jalalain.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Human Resource Management

Management functions (POAC) are necessary to manage organizational resources so that management can achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently. Management and administration of human resources through organizational and operational functions are interrelated. Marwansyah stated that career planning and development, recruitment and selection, human resource development, welfare and compensation, and occupational safety and health are all included in an organization's human resource development process. This process is referred to as management. According to Flippo, To achieve individual and organizational goals, personnel management, also known as human resource management, is planning, organizing, directing, and terminating employment relationships and developing compensation, integrating, maintaining, and terminating employment relationships. Working relationship with human resources. Community goals. To achieve organizational goals, human resource management is the process of planning, staffing, coordinating, and monitoring the acquisition, distribution, and development of the workforce. (Wilson, 2012).

Human resource management ensures that every aspect of an organization's human affairs actively advances the achievement of its stated goals. The process of carrying out management tasks such as organizing, planning, directing, and monitoring is known as human resource management. Achieving personal and company goals requires effective and efficient support. Thus, an organization can operate efficiently if its human resources are managed and utilized well. An organization's human resource management department oversees human resource management procedures. This department is critical to an organization's efforts to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of its human resource management. The term "human resources management" refers to a variety of concepts and practices, including rules and procedures that must be followed to fulfill a manager's responsibilities related to human resources (Samsuni, 2017).

Quality Improvement

In educational management, quality improvement is characterized as combining concepts and techniques that emphasize raising teaching standards by relying on academic institutions to consistently increase their capacity and ability to meet the demands of society and students. This allows these companies to deal with the impacts of globalization effectively. With viability, high-quality students will be produced, and user or stakeholder satisfaction will be achieved. The linguistic term "quality improvement" is formed by combining the words "quality" and "improvement." The word "improvement" describes practices, plans, or actions that promote growth (of a business, activity, etc.). However, the degree, grade, or quality (measure) of whether an object is good or bad is what is meant by the definition of its quality. (Ihsan, 2017). The definition of quality in the educational context includes input, process, and output. In the academic context, everything needed for a process to take place is considered input, be it students, lecturers, staff, facilities, and infrastructure. Any procedures used to produce the highest quality results, including monitoring, evaluation, and so on, are referred to as "processes." Meanwhile, outputs such as student achievement and other metrics result from educational institutions' efforts to improve their teaching standards.

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Productive Environmental Education

Productivity is integrating and applying all production techniques to improve managerial functions, create work systems and related tasks, and recognize individuals who can be trusted by considering the surrounding environment. Support from school administrators, teachers, support staff, students, and parents is needed to increase productivity because this support can foster an environment that encourages student achievement and skills in improving the standards of educational institutions.

Strategies for Improving the Quality of a Productive Educational Environment

Strategy is a series of planned actions or steps to achieve specific goals. Achieving intended goals requires selecting resources, assigning resources, and coordinating actions. In general, the strategy includes: Identifying the goals to be achieved, Assessing the external factors that influence those goals, Organizing the actions to be taken to achieve those goals. Achieve that goal. Proper resource allocation involves people, money, time, and other assets. In the process of increasing environmental productivity, there are several strategies for doing so, namely:

A broad-minded leader

Leadership is about solving problems, being a visionary, and bringing about change. As a leader's role develops, their actions also develop.(Rustamadji, 2020). Insightful leaders can see the broader picture and understand how their choices affect their organization's internal and external environments. Insightful leaders can recognize potential opportunities and challenges in the future. They are also able to combine different points of view to produce original and long-lasting solutions.(Hamandia, 2021). In the Islamic view, leaders who have broad insight can be categorized into various characteristics, namely: (1) Shidiq (honest) Leaders who prioritize moral integrity (morals), only words and deeds, honesty, and ethical attitudes and behavior are prioritized by this leadership. In thinking, acting, and behaving, honesty is an intangible value that loves and refers to the truth that comes from Allah SWT. As stated in QS. An-Najm:3-4. (2) Amanah(Trusted) Muhammad was the first person to enter the square (the Kaaba quadrangle) through a certain door, and it was decided that he should be asked to be a peacemaker. So, Trustworthiness is a necessary trait for a leader. Because of his trustworthy nature, the leader will always uphold the public's faith in him, which has been bestowed upon him as a noble trust. Have faith in the community by entrusting its leaders to manage all affairs and benefit everyone. As stated in the Al-Qur'an surah Al-Qasas 26. (3) Tablig (Communicative) A leader needs to have the potential and basic qualities of communication skills. A leader will face various societal tendencies when carrying out his mandate for the benefit of the people. Therefore, effective communication is the secret to building strong relationships between leaders and their people, as Allah says in QS. Al. Maidah verse 27. (4) Fathonah (intelligent) A visionary leader must be knowledgeable, intelligent, creative, open-minded, and have a long-term perspective. Because bold, creative thinking and practical action are needed to achieve the benefit and welfare of society. In this context, intelligence refers to all forms of intelligence, including intellectual, spiritual, and emotional intelligence. The degree of intelligence a leader possesses significantly influences the perception of that leader among his followers and creators. Insightful leaders can see the broader picture and understand how their choices affect their organization's internal and external environments. They can recognize potential opportunities and challenges in the future and combine different points of view to produce original and long-lasting solutions.(Saputra, 2016). As the word of Allah explains in QS. Mujjadi verse 11.

Effective classroom management

The teacher's ability to maintain order and foster a positive learning environment. The teacher will facilitate an effective and efficient teaching and learning process in a conducive classroom.(Nova Yanti, 2016). Classroom management is, of course, inseparable from the supervision of the principal; the principal must provide continuous and continuous supervision to help teachers grow and become better at their work. Observing The primary purpose is to instruct and enhance learning.(Warsono, 2016).

Supporting facilities

The teaching resources used, as well as teachers' and students' participation in learning activities, significantly influence achieving learning objectives. Apart from providing guidance and comfort during learning activities, these teaching materials speed up and increase the accuracy of student learning outcomes. To achieve good learning outcomes for students, which is a sign of teacher success in their performance and continues to develop and improve in the school where the researcher conducted the research, it is hoped that learning facilities can be utilized effectively.(Nuzli, 2021).

Building a positive school culture

School culture, namely the environment in which students, teachers, counselors, administrative staff, and members of school community groups interact, is one way to help build character in students. On the other hand, school culture covers a wide range of topics, including customs, expectations, relationships, demographics, extracurricular and curricular activities, policies, decision-making procedures, and social interactions among the various components of the school. Fostering a culture of mutual

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respect and cooperation among students by building a positive learning environment is one way to help develop character in students.(Pradana, 2016). This strategy will work if a leader or principal is strong-willed, understands educators' working conditions in other institutions, has short-term and long-term programs, is visionary, makes the right decisions, and communicates effectively with all members. school community.(Muhtar, 2015).

Challenges in Improving the Quality of a Productive Educational Environment

The most critical factors in Indonesian educational institutions are quality, relevance, efficiency, productivity, and effectiveness. The causes are a need for more student enrollment and academic achievement, both in quantity and quality, and inadequate student support. Challenges in the process of improving the quality of the productive educational environment include(Dacholfany, 2017):

Leadership and Management

Success in improving the quality of human resources in educational institutions is a primary concern for leaders and leadership staff. Leaders will become frustrated and lose trust in other academic institutions if they are flexible, experienced, and persistent in their leadership. Good leaders have systematic characteristics and qualities: (1)Have a quality vision and mission to achieve the desired goals, (2)Able to manage existing resources, (3)Support and facilitate necessary needs, (4)Able to communicate well. School management determines the success of a school institution because, with quality management, the school's goals can be achieved well by national standards set by the government. If school management is not implemented well, there will be delays in the development of the quality of education.

Quality of Educator Staff

The quality of teaching staff is needed to develop students' potential and improve the quality of educational institutions. Poorly qualified teaching staff can have an impact on reducing students' enthusiasm for creating productive learning skills. As educators, teachers greatly influence the creation of a superior learning process. To develop the learning process in schools, teachers must have a foundation for creative and innovative thinking. Teachers who can develop learning and have the empowerment to do so are critical to fostering students' creative thinking. The empowerment of their competencies influences educator performance and the quality of education. Professional teachers must be competent to fulfill their roles and contribute to school goals. In measuring the quality of educators, there are several steps: (a) teaching ability, (b) communication skills, (c) understanding of student needs, (d) experience in teaching, and (e) concern for educational development.

Lack of facilities and infrastructure

A lack of infrastructure and facilities can hinder the development of a productive and quality learning environment in the educational context. Inadequate facilities and infrastructure at school, of course, influence student learning outcomes. In other words, the existence and completeness of educational facilities and infrastructure support teachers in dealing with learning problems and implementing education in schools. To be able to motivate students and arouse interest in learning while saving time preparing material, teaching and learning activities must utilize teaching aids and tools that are useful along with advances in science and technology. The teaching and learning process must be followed as closely as possible to produce learning outcomes that align with the educational goals developed previously. The many parts of learning as a system are objectives, media, techniques, content or materials, and assessment.(Lestari, 2021). Maintaining educational success requires adequate infrastructure and facilities; in this case, poor quality or lack of access can impact student outcomes and the teaching and learning process.

Compensation

Providing rewards or compensation to teaching staff and other employees in educational institutions for their work is called compensation. Salaries, allowances, bonuses, and other incentives are just some compensation components in academic institutions. These components are given to people who help carry out various tasks and functions required in running and managing educational institutions. Providing fair and competitive compensation can help educational institutions attract and retain the best educators. If good compensation is provided, teaching and learning activities and educational service processes will be improved, and difficulties will be experienced.

Challenges in Improving the Quality of a Productive Educational Environment in Islamic Educational Institutions

There are several challenges in improving the quality of a productive educational environment in Islamic academic institutions, namely:

Weak institutional vision and mission

Education managers often need to pay more attention to the important task of identifying the vision and mission of their institutions. The mission statement of an educational institution should be created to be the cornerstone of the learning process. An educational institution can plan and determine what is needed for educational activities with the help of its vision and mission

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statement. The current vision and mission are a source of great difficulty for Islamic educational institutions. Educational institutions whose task is to achieve national education standards are to carry out their duties well. To fulfill its role as a learning environment, schools must be managed effectively to achieve the best educational outcomes. Incompetent school administration can hinder the school's efforts to fulfill its role as a formal educational institution and the ongoing educational process.

Overloaded Curriculum

One of the most pressing problems in education is the curriculum. There must be more overlap between religious and general lessons in the madrasa curriculum, which contains material. The madrasa curriculum places more emphasis on the cognitive domain than the affective or psychomotor domain. The curriculum needs to be immediately improved because Islamic educational institutions must operate with a balanced curriculum. Setting and achieving academic goals will be a challenge. The design of the Islamic education curriculum must also expand its content to include matters related to learning objectives and the educational process to meet the demands of a rapidly developing field.

Low competitiveness of graduates of educational institutions

Madrasa graduates are very different from state school graduates because madrasas offer more comprehensive religious education than public schools, so they have more advantages. This shows that madrasas are the main place of moral education in religious education. However, madrasas still have weaknesses when competing with state school graduates.(Rahman & Akbar, 2021).

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An Overview of Tafsir Jalalain

This Tafsir Jalalain is a commentary on the work of Imam Jalaludin As-Suyuthi and Imam Jalaluddin Al-Mahalli Tafsir Jalalain. Tafsir Jalalain is the term given to this book of Tafsir, which is given to the two authors of Jalal. However, Tafsir al-Quran al-Adzim should be the original name of this tafsir. In 791 H/1389 AD, Jalaluddin Al-Mahalli was born in Cairo, Egypt. He is referred to as Al-Mahalli, and he represents the village. His yard is close to the Nile River, west of Cairo. Meanwhile, his full name is Jalaluddin Al-Mahalli, Muhammad bin Ahmad bin Ibrahim bin Ahmad Al-Imam Allamah Jalaluddin Al-Mahalli. Al-Mahalli is considered a famous cleric, and his understanding of Islamic issues is beyond doubt. Some even describe it as brighter than diamonds. Meanwhile, Jalaluddin As-Suyuthi was born in 849 H in Rajab. Abu Al-Fadhl Abdurrahman bin Abi Bakar bin Muhammad AsSuyuthi As-Syafi'i is his full name. In 849 H.S, he was born in the month of Rajab. He got the nickname Jalaluddin from his father, who gave it to him. Meanwhile, As-Suyuthi is the area's name, which was later given the name Asyut. Like Al-Mahalli, As-Suyuthi is a respected scholar with a deep understanding. At the age of eight, he could memorize the Koran. He also memorized other hadiths and used the names Musnid and Muhaqqiq.(Ikhsanul Faqih, 2021).

Starting in the middle of Juz fifteen, in Surah al-Kahf, Imam Jalaluddin al-Mahalli wrote his tafsir and traced it backward until he reached the last surah, Surah An-Nas verse 25. He continued his understanding of Surah al-Fatihah after translating Surah al-Kahf into Surah An-Nas. He plans to explain the other letters to completion, starting with Surah al-Fatihah. However, in 864 H/1445 AD, he died. Jalaluddin al-Suyuti then continued, refining his teacher's views. After Ramadan 870 H, Jalaluddin al-Suyuti completed the idea of the tafsir within 40 days and finished it a year later. This Tafsir Jalalain consists of 2, namely, Tafsir Jalalain Volume 1 and Volume 2.(Zuman malaka, 2023).

Totality in Human Resources Development

Totality is an attitude or behavior shown completely, selflessly, and with unwavering dedication. This idea is often used in various contexts, such as the workplace, art, sports, and everyday life. A totalitarian directs all his efforts to achieve the greatest possible results. Minor distractions and obstacles do not affect them. Instead, they concentrate on the work or activity at hand. Significant achievements and extraordinary performance can result from a totality-oriented mindset. But keep in mind that totality can also affect life balance. Therefore, it is very important to maintain harmony and health while achieving your goals in total. According to Sastradipoera, Education, and training that aims to improve general knowledge of the surrounding environment or carry out training for special tasks are all included in human resource development.(Anisatul Maghfiroh, 2021).

Development and improvement of human resources can be done through various strategies, including education. By focusing on developing basic traits such as personality, faith and purity, intelligence, discipline, creativity, and so on, this education aims to improve the quality of human resources. Education plays an important role as an investment in the future and has strategic value in developing human resources. Theoretically, education is the basis for economic expansion, scientific and technological progress, reducing income gaps and poverty, and improving human civilization (Walidin, 2016).

The completeness of educational human resource development shows dedication to the overall development of students. This strategy emphasizes social skills development, building academic strengths, and monitoring emotional health. Teachers and other education professionals have a role in inspiring students to realize their full potential by offering inclusive and encouraging

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learning opportunities. Understanding each person's individuality and totality makes room for personal development, leadership, and empowerment. Wholeness-based education prepares students to face big challenges in the classroom and shapes them into people who make valuable contributions to society. Therefore, totality is an important foundation for building a strong and capable generation.

The Al-Qur'an explains the Totality of Human Resources Development in Surah Al-An'am, verse 162 :

قُلْ إِنَّ صَلَاتِي وَنُسُكِي وَمَحْيَايَ وَمَمَاتِي لِلَّهِ رَبِّ الْعَالَمِينَ

It means : Say, "Indeed, my prayer, my worship, my life and my death are only for Allah, the Lord of the worlds".

According to the study of Tafsir Jalalain, it explains about (say, "Indeed, my prayers, my worship) my deeds of worship, namely the Hajj and other things (my life) my life (and my death) leaving me (only for Allah, the Lord of the worlds). (Tafsir Jalalain,).

Analyzing the material in verse above with human resources means that to produce high-quality results from our efforts, we must give our all in everything we do, wherever we are. To increase productivity and the quality of the educational environment, all educational institutions seriously strive for this quality in their human resources.

Justice in Human Resource Management

According to Long, human resource management differs from personnel management, which experiences problems of injustice due to organizational justice. The aspect of organizational justice is very important for the existence of an organization because, if there is no justice, there may be a decrease in commitment, an increase in workplace crime, and a tendency to protest. Organizational commitment is positively influenced by organizational justice. (Kristanto, 2015).

Single human resource management includes all the activities involved in human resource management. Wijayanto emphasized that resource management, the process of human resource activities, is connected to the management function. Human, which includes recruiting, selecting, preparing, and developing staff members. According to Marihot Tua, human resource management is a series of actions taken to build, grow, inspire, and uphold an environment that enables the achievement of high performance within the company. (Cahya et al., 2021).

In the Al-Qur'an, it is explained in surah Al-Maidah verse 8 regarding the concept of justice in the management of human resources, namely:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا كُونُوا قَوَّامِينَ لِلَّهِ شُهَدَاءَ بِالْقِسْطِ وَلَا يَجْرِمَنَّكُمْ شَنَاَنُ قَوْمٍ عَلَىٰ أَلَّا تَعْدِلُوا ۗ اعْدِلُوا هُوَ أَقْرَبُ لِلتَّقْوَىٰ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ إِنَّ اللَّهَ خَبِيرٌ بِمَا تَعْمَلُونَ

It means : O you who believe, be you upholders of (the truth) for Allah (and) witnesses (who act) fairly. Don't let your hatred of a people encourage you to act unfairly. Be fair because (fair) is closer to piety. Have faith in Allah. Indeed, Allah is careful about what you do.

According to the study of Tafsir Jalalain, for those who believe, may you always be by Allah's side, proclaiming His truth and giving testimony fairly. Refrain from acting unjustly towards disbelievers until you have persecuted them because of their hostility (be just towards you); this will bring justice (because it is closer to righteousness) to your enemies and your friends. And fear Allah (indeed, He is All-Knowing of everything you do) to avoid His wrath. (Tafsir Jalalain,).

Material analysis: This verse highlights the relationship between righteousness and Justice. This can be understood in the context of human resources, meaning that moral and spiritual values will be strengthened in the workplace by implementing Justice. The Qur'an's emphasis on the principles of Justice makes this verse clear. Justice in the context of human resources is the fair application of laws and regulations to every educational institution without regard to factors such as gender, race, ethnicity, or religion.

Responsibility and Trust in Human Resource Development

Taking responsibility for one's decisions or actions is required by law or morality. It shows how ready someone or something is to live life with the results of their actions. Accountability includes ethical, communal, and work aspects when engaging with others or completing tasks. High levels of responsibility develop individual or organizational integrity and build a foundation of trust in interpersonal relationships. As a basis for professional and personal development, responsibility highlights the importance of accountability in achieving shared goals. Therefore, cultivating a sense of responsibility is essential for society to function. The acquisition of quantity and quality knowledge is closely related to the development of human resources. This is a very important situation because knowledge provides a basis for people to act and allows them to improve their quality of life. Therefore, it is important to develop existing human resources to improve welfare. Human resource development is very important because it is a key component in increasing productivity. It also has certain goals that must be met to progress a country's development. (Effendi, 2021).

Creating a superior and competitive generation depends on human resource (HR) development accountability in the education sector. Adequate learning facilities, high-quality teacher preparation, and a relevant curriculum are guarantees of responsible education. These duties include upholding student rights, managing inclusivity, and fostering a safe and encouraging learning environment. Education is tasked with creating humans who can face future challenges by emphasizing the development of

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critical and creative competencies. Therefore, accountability for human resource development in education is a wise investment in creating a culture that values intelligence and excellence.

In the Al-Qur'an, it is explained in surah Al-Ahzab 33:72 regarding the concept of responsibility and trust, namely:

إِنَّا عَرَضْنَا الْأَمَانَةَ عَلَى السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ وَالْجِبَالِ فَأَبَيْنَ أَنْ يَحْمِلْنَهَا وَأَشْفَقْنَ مِنْهَا وَحَمَلَهَا الْإِنْسَانُ إِنَّهُ كَانَ ظَلُومًا جَهُولًا

It means: *Indeed, we have offered a mandate to the heavens, the earth, and the mountains, but all of them were reluctant to assume the mandate and were afraid they would not carry it out. Then, the mandate was carried by humans. Indeed, he (man) is very unjust and very stupid.*

According to the study of Tafsir Jalalain, namely, Indeed, We have given the mandate, prayer, and other acts of worship; if followed, the disobedient will be rewarded; If it is not followed, the disobedient person will be punished (in the heavens, on earth and the mountains). For example, Allah gave each of them the ability to understand and speak; However, because of this, they were all reluctant to carry out this mandate for fear of being betrayed. Humans carried out this trust through the Prophet Adam, who initially offered it (yes, humans are very unfair) to himself. As a result of what he experienced (again, very stupidly), he didn't realize what he was carrying. (Tafsir Jalalain,).

Material analysis, namely the Islamic context, emphasizes responsibility and trust and views them as important components of religious values. These values can help society fulfill its obligations with justice, integrity, and honesty regarding human resource development. An educational environment that encourages productivity and quality improvement is created through the complementary role of justice in management and human resource management. All members of an academic community are more likely to positively impact an organization's goals and vision when they perceive fair treatment, support, and recognition.

Increased Potential in Supporting Human Resource Management

A person's potential is their ability to develop and be realized. According to Purwanto, the potential is "all the possibilities or skills that a person has and that, over time and development, can be truly realized. A person's potential is a fundamental ability that is still latent but has the potential to develop with the right role, environment, facilities, and training. Encouraging students to reach their full potential is so important in education; in fact, it is the main goal of teaching. So that students can reach their maximum potential, it is important to recognize and understand the potential that exists within themselves. Student potential has not been fully realized or utilized. This occurs due to the need for more knowledge of their potential and internal obstacles that prevent them from reaching their maximum potential. The right help is needed to maximize student potential and provide understanding.

The environment can have a direct or indirect impact on the educational process. It is impossible to quantify the exact amount of influence each environment has. Still, the effect of these settings is very important and has the same goals as the aspirations of states, nations, and religions. So, that's the goal. Students are the main concern. Students' potential in learning must be connected to obtaining an overview of students. Therefore, the aim of education for humans as a whole and for life is to help humans develop their personality potential by their nature and essence, maximizing their performance in all areas. (Amaliyah & Rahmat, 2021).

In the Al-Qur'an, the concept of developing potential is explained in surah Al-Baqarah 2:286 :

إِنَّا يَكْفِيكَ اللَّهُ نَفْسًا إِلَّا وُسْعَهَا لَهَا مَا كَسَبَتْ وَعَلَيْهَا مَا اكْتَسَبَتْ رَبَّنَا لَا تُؤَاخِذْنَا إِنْ نَسِينَا أَوْ أَخْطَأْنَا رَبَّنَا وَلَا تَحْمِلْ عَلَيْنَا إصْرًا كَمَا حَمَلْتَهُ عَلَى الَّذِينَ مِنْ قَبْلِنَا رَبَّنَا وَلَا تُحَمِّلْنَا مَا لَا طَاقَةَ لَنَا بِهِ وَاعْفُ عَنَّا وَارْحَمْنَا أَنْتَ مَوْلَانَا فَانصُرْنَا عَلَى الْقَوْمِ الْكَافِرِينَ

It means : *Allah does not burden a person except according to his ability. For him, there is something (reward) for the (virtue) he strives for, and for him, there is (also) something (torment) for the (crime) he commits. (They prayed.) "O our Lord, do not punish us if we forget or are wrong. O our Lord, do not burden us with heavy burdens as you burdened those before us. O our Lord, do not bear what we cannot bear for us. Forgive us, forgive us, and have mercy on us. You are our protector. So, could you help us in facing the disbelievers?."*

According to the study of Tafsir Jalalain, namely burdening a person according to his ability) showing his ability alone (what he obtained from his hard work) in the form of virtue, showing his reward (which he also received from the consequences of his transgressions, especially his sins). As a result, a person does not bear the consequences for actions he did not commit; instead, it remains a dream. They begged, "Our Lord, save us from the punishment of torment (if we forget or are guilty)," which means abandoning the truth to no purpose, as was the punishment meted out to those before us. As explained in the hadith, Allah has taken this from this Ummah. By asking the children of Israel to commit suicide as a sign of repentance, donating a quarter of their wealth for zakat, and digging up unclean places, we acknowledge the blessings of Allah (O our Lord, do not burden us with a heavy burden) that we cannot bear. May bear (as you forced upon those before you).

As a protector, the material analysis reflects the need for support and protection to increase potential. Good human resource management also includes empowerment and protection of human resource rights. Allah does not burden a person beyond his ability. In human resources, potential development must be adjusted to each individual's skills and potential.

Human Resource Management in Improving The Quality of A Productive Educational Environment From Al-Qur'an Perspective; Analysis of Jalalain's Tafsir

Participation in Improving Human Resources

Participation comes from the word participate, which means "to include." "A number of people taking part in an activity; inclusion" is intended in the Big Indonesian Dictionary by inclusion. Participation can also mean that decision-makers suggest that citizens or groups contribute ideas, opinions, products, services, skills, materials, and Projects to achieve community development goals. In a democratic environment, participation can take many forms, such as ideas, services, or materials offered directly or indirectly. Parental participation, on the other hand, can be understood as parents' awareness of the importance of caring for their children and playing an active role in overcoming problems related to the provision of education related to meeting their needs materially and emotionally.

Parental involvement in their children's education at school is divided into two categories: material and non-material (moral). Parental material participation includes providing financial support through teacher honorariums, practicum funds, assistance in purchasing or procuring children's educational tools and equipment, and assistance in the form of goods (school infrastructure, aid, equipment, and learning media). On the other hand, involvement in non-marital (moral) forms includes any assistance intended to achieve school program goals, such as offering ideas, thoughts, and suggestions for program progress, inspiring teachers and students to increase learning achievement, and providing support and attention on children's learning difficulties.(Ayudia, 2014).

Surah Ali-Imran 3:104 explains the concept of participation and involvement in the Al-Qur'an:

وَلْتَكُنْ مِنْكُمْ أُمَّةٌ يَدْعُونَ إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ

It means : *There should be among you a group of people who call to virtue, enjoin (do) what is virtuous, and forbid what is evil. They are the lucky people.*

According to the study of Tafsir Jalalain, groups among you forbid evil and encourage good, proclaiming the goodness of Islamic teachings. These people are known as those who are lucky, those who forbid, and those who order.(*Terjemah Tafsir Jalalain Jilid 2.*).

Material analysis conveys an understanding of Muslims' duties and responsibilities to promote wealth and thwart crime. One way to view involvement in human resource development is as an obligation to improve the living standards of individuals and society. Apart from that, there is a way to achieve this goal, namely by actively participating in the learning, training, and education process.

CONCLUSION

From the discussion above, it can be concluded that to improve the educational environment, productivity is found in Q.S Al-An'am 6:162, Q.S Al-Maidah 5:8, Q.S Al-Ahzab 33:72, Q.S Al-Baqarah 2: 286, Q.S Ali-Imran 3:104 which can be formulated regarding several strategies: a) totality in human resource development, b) justice in human resource management, c) responsibility and trust in human resource development, d) improvement potential in supporting human resource management and e) participation in improving human resources. Through this implementation, an educational institution can strive to increase the efficiency of the learning environment to support improving the institution's quality.

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